

CHARACTERISATION OF NEW GENERATION SMALL DIAMETER SiC FIBRES AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

N. Hochet, M. H. Berger & A. R. Bunsell

Ecole des Mines de Paris Centre des Matériaux, BP 87, 91003 Evry Cedex, France

SUMMARY: The new generation of small diameter SiC based fibres contains markedly less oxygen than similar fibres presently in use. The effect of the oxygen content is known to create an intergranular metastable phase which limits use at high temperature and encourages creep. The reduction in oxygen in the Hi-Nicalon fibre is shown to increase the rigidity and to improve creep behaviour. In the Tyranno Lox-E fibre the reduction is still not sufficient to eliminate the effects of the intergranular phase and behaviour is seen to be similar to the previous generation of fibres.

KEYWORDS: Hi-Nicalon, Tyranno Lox-M, Tyranno Lox-E, ceramic fibre, silicon carbide, microstructure, mechanical properties, high temperature

INTRODUCTION

The development of fine and flexible fibres based on silicon carbide offers the possibility of reinforcing ceramic materials to produce high temperature structural composites. Nicalon NLM202 has been available since the early 1980s. Its microstructure has been described as consisting of β -SiC grains of 1.6 μ m diameter (55%wt) and free carbon (5%wt) embedded in an intergranular phase SiO_xC_y (40%wt) [1]. The differences between the mechanical characteristics and thermal stability of stoichiometric SiC and the SiC based ceramic from PCS are due to the existence of the intergranular phase and free carbon [2]. The Si-C-O phase allows the ceramic to creep and this is observed from 1273K. The free carbon reduces the oxidation resistance of the fibre. A fall in properties is observed associated with the decomposition of the intergranular phase and the microstructural changes.

Significant improvement of the high-temperature mechanical properties of SiC based fibres might be expected if the oxygen content could be reduced or the intergranular phase stabilised. The aim of this paper is to establish the consequences of a lower oxygen content and/or the presence of titanium on the microstructure and thermomechanical properties of the most recent polymer derived SiC based fibres.

MATERIALS

The most widely used fibres based on SiC are produced by Nippon Carbon (Nicalon fibres) and Ube Industries (Tyranno fibres) from respectively, polycarbosilane (PCS) and polytitanocarbosilane (PTC) polymer fibres. These precursor fibres are melt-spun and cross-

linked in air for the Nicalon NLM202 and the Tyranno Lox-M, or by electron beam irradiation in a helium atmosphere for the Hi-Nicalon and the Tyranno Lox-E fibres. The green fibres are then pyrolysed between 1473K and 1673K in an inert atmosphere. The main characteristics of the fibres given by the manufacturers are presented in Table 1. The precursor of the Tyranno fibres is different from that used for the Nicalon fibres, (PTC and PCS, respectively). According to Ube Industries, the presence of titanium stabilises the amorphous phase and so limits grain growth and the degradation of mechanical properties. Another effect of titanium could be the creation of Ti-C bonds, so offering better oxidation resistance, as the amount of free carbon at the interface would be reduced [4].

Table 1: Physical and chemical data on the fibres studied as given by the manufacturers [5,6]

	NLM 202	Hi-Nicalon	Tyranno Lox M	Tyranno Lox-E
Precursor	PCS	PCS	PTC	PTC
Cross linking mode	oxidation curing	radiation curing	oxidation curing	radiation curing
Diameter (μm)	15	13	8.5	11
Density (g/cm^3)	2.55	2.74	2.37	2.39
% Si wt	56.6	62.4	54.0	54.8
% C wt	31.7	37.1	31.6	37.5
% O wt	11.7	0.5	12.4	5.8
% Ti wt	0	0	2.0	1.9
C/Si at	1.31	1.39	1.36	1.64

The industrially produced Nicalon NLM202 and Tyranno Lox-M fibres, referred to here as "the present generation" have a high oxygen content (12 to 13% wt). The new generation of fibres contains less oxygen, Tyranno Lox-E (~ 5 %wt) and Hi-Nicalon (~ 0,5%wt), as the precursors have been crosslinked in the absence of oxygen. The carbon to oxygen ratio is greater in these fibres than in fibres cured by oxidation for which a part of carbon is eliminated in the form of carbon oxides during pyrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

The microstructures of these fibres were observed by transmission electron microscopy using an ARM working at 800 kV. Thin specimens were prepared by argon ion milling. Fracture morphologies were observed by scanning electron microscopy. The microscopes used were a Phillips 501 and a LEO Gemini 982 which was equipped with a field effect gun.

Mechanical tests were made with a mono-filamentary tensile machine equipped with a furnace allowing tests to be conducted from room temperature to 1673K in air and in flowing argon. The gauge length used for the tensile tests at room temperature was 25mm. For tests at higher temperatures, with cold jaws and in air, the gauge length was 250mm. The section heated at the maximum temperature was 30mm in length. The displacement speed for tensile tests was 0.2 mm/min. The fibres were heated for three minutes before the start of the tensile tests. As each test lasted about 5 minutes, each fibre spent an average of 8 minutes at the test temperature. Creep tests were conducted for a period of one or three days, in an argon flow.

RESULTS

Appearance of The Fibres

All the fibres had the same external appearance, they were circular in cross section , with a smooth surface and showed the same featureless morphology at the surface and core (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Fracture morphology at room temperature

Tensile Properties at Room Temperature

All the fibres showed linear elastic behaviour at room temperature and their failure surfaces were characteristic of brittle failure (Fig. 1). The mechanical properties of these fibres at room temperature are shown in Fig 2. The fibres with a low oxygen content had elastic moduli and failure stresses which were higher than the present generation fibres. Within the same generation of fibres, the Tyranno fibres had higher failure stresses than the Nicalon fibres.

Fig. 2: Failure stress and elastic modulus of the Nicalon and Tyranno fibres

Tensile Behaviour at High Temperature

The variations of the strengths of the fibres, tested in air, as a function of temperature are presented in Fig. 3. The decrease of the failure stress was seen to occur at lower temperatures

for the Tyranno fibres. The evolution of the failure stresses of the NLM202 and Hi-Nicalon fibres were almost parallel, with higher values for the Hi-Nicalon.

Fig.3: Evolution of tensile strengths as a function of temperature for the NLM 202, Hi-Nicalon, Lox-M and Lox-E fibres.

Creep Behaviour

Shrinkage at high temperature

Creep experiments at high temperatures and low loads revealed that negative strains were obtained at the beginning of the tests which influenced the creep curves obtained. An indication of the maximum stresses for which negative strains were detected is given in Table 2. The amount of shrinkage for a given stress increased as the temperature increased, as shown in Fig.4 but the stress for which only positive strains were obtained decreased as the temperature increased. The Nicalon fibres did not show negative deformation up to 1423K indicating no or very little shrinkage of these fibres up to this temperature. Above 1423K the Nicalon fibres began to shrink significantly. Shrinkage of the Tyranno fibres during creep experiments was observed from around 1323K and the amount of negative deformation, especially for the Lox-M fibre, were higher than that seen with the Nicalon fibres. This shrinkage during creep could be suppressed by a heat treatment of the fibres prior to mechanical testing. This is illustrated in Fig. 5 which shows results obtained with Tyranno Lox M fibres, before and after heat treatment at 1473K in argon for 5 hours (Tyranno Lox-MA). Similar stabilisation of the Hi-Nicalon could be obtained but heat treatment temperatures above 1400°C were necessary. The elastic moduli of the Lox-M fibres increased from 180 GPa to 193 GPa after heat treatment at 1473K. The effects of heat treatments on the elastic modulus of the Hi-Nicalon fibre are shown in Fig 6. It can be seen that the increase in modulus is accompanied by a decrease in strength.

Table 2: Maximum stresses σ_{max} (GPa) for which shrinkage was detected

Temperature (K)	NLM 202	Hi-Nicalon	Lox-M	Lox-E
1323	no shrinkage	no shrinkage	1.00	1.05
1423	no shrinkage	no shrinkage	0.65	0.45
1523	0.34	0.29	0.40	0.27
1623	0.18	0.20	0.08	0.20
1723	0.06	0.04	0.19	0.07

Fig.4: Shrinkage during creep increases with temperature.

Fig. 5: Shrinkage during creep of the Lox-M b) is suppressed by a heat treatment of the fibres prior to testing a).

Fig.6: Variation of the rigidity and strength of the Hi-Nicalon fibre after heat-treatments.

Creep behaviour

All the fibres crept at high temperatures when under load. Their creep curves exhibited primary creep which lasted approximately five hours followed by secondary creep stages which was pseudo-stationary stage up to 1473-1573K, depending on the fibre type. Beyond these temperatures the creep rate is seen to be truly stationary. Fig.7 shows the creep behaviour of the Hi-Nicalon fibre at different temperatures subjected to approximately the same load. No third stage creep was observed.

Fig. 7: Examples of creep curves for the Hi-Nicalon fibre obtained with an applied stress of ≈ 0.45 GPa

Fig.8 : Logarithmic plot of strain rates as a function of the applied stress at 1323K and 1723K for the fibres studied

Fig. 8 represents the deformation rates of the fibres respectively at 1323K and 1723K between 10 and 16 hours after the start of the creep study, for different applied stresses. Experimental limitations meant that the lowest deformation rate was 10^{-10}s^{-1} . The points shown on the curves corresponding to the threshold limit reflect therefore a rate of 10^{-10}s^{-1} . The rate of deformation, shown in Fig.8 corresponding to results obtained at 1323K, reveals the existence of creep thresholds which are high compared to the fibre failure stress. It must be noted that the Lox-M fibres show a higher creep threshold stress than the Lox-E fibres. Just above the threshold stress for the Lox-M fibre the latter creeps at a lower rate than the Lox-E fibre at the same stress. As the applied stress is increased further from the threshold level the creep rate curve for the Lox-M fibre crosses the curve for the Lox-E fibre to become greater. The creep behaviour of the NLM202 fibre can be seen from Fig.8 to be placed between that of the Lox-E and Lox-M fibres. However the Hi-Nicalon fibre possesses the highest creep threshold stress of all the fibres at 1323K and creeps at a much lower rate.

The Lox-M fibres which had been subjected to heat treatments at 1473K for 5 hours (Lox-MA) showed rates of deformation which were lower than those of the Lox-M and the NLM 202 fibres.

With increasing temperature, up to 1723K, the creep threshold stresses of all the fibres reduced. The strain rate of the Hi-Nicalon remained lower than the other fibres but the differences in creep behaviour became much less marked. Fig.8 shows the similar creep rates observed with all the fibres at 1723K.

Microstructures of the Fibres

The microstructures of the Lox-M and the Lox-E fibres, appeared similar and consisted of nanometric β -SiC grains of 2 nm in diameter and free carbon of around 1 nm in length as illustrated in Fig. 9 [7]. These microstructures were comparable to that observed with NLM202 fibres, although some larger grains up to 5 nm were found in the Lox-E fibres.

Fig. 9: Microstructure of the Lox-E fibre.

No crystallised Ti compounds were found in the as received Tyranno fibres and the titanium was assumed to be distributed inside an intergranular phase $\text{SiC}_x\text{Ti}_y\text{O}_z$ although such a phase could not be directly detected by TEM. The Hi-Nicalon fibre was distinguished from the other fibres by larger SiC grains (Fig. 10). The average grain size was about 5nm in the Hi-Nicalon but grains of up to 20nm in diameter existed, and the structure appeared to be a continuum of lattice-imaged SiC grains. Free carbon aggregates embedded in the SiC continuum exhibited better organisation in the Hi-Nicalon compared to the other fibres. They appear on lattice fringe images by the stacking of slightly distorted 5 to 10 carbon layers with a length of from 2nm up to 5nm [7].

Fig. 10: Microstructure of the Hi-Nicalon fibre.

Modification of the microstructures of the fibres at high temperatures

After being heat treated for 24 hours in air above 1473K all the fibres were coated with SiO₂. At 1673K, the layer was completely crystallised into cristobalite and cracked. Some micropores could be seen in this layer and at the fibre-oxide interface (Fig. 11). A similar layer could be seen on fracture surfaces of the fibres tested at high temperatures. Fracture initiation in all the fibres tested in air was located at the SiO₂/fibre interface. The fracture morphologies at high temperatures were as brittle as those obtained at room temperature. The non oxidised part of the fibre within the silica layer can be seen from Fig. 18 to be no longer circular. The fracture behaviour of the fibres after creep in flowing argon was seen to remain brittle. A very thin SiO₂ layer could be seen on the surface of these fibres due to the presence of a low partial oxygen pressure.

Some grain growth was observed after heat treatment in air from 1373K for the Tyranno fibres and from 1573K for the Nicalon fibres. The relative grain growth for the NLM202 was 25%, for the Hi-Nicalon 55%, for the Lox-M 63% and for the Lox-E 90% after five hours at 1673K. At this temperature regions showing a continuum of SiC grains were observed in all the fibres. Growth of the free carbon aggregates was seen in all the fibres with the increase of the temperature and this carbon was frequently seen to surround SiC grains in the Hi-Nicalon fibres. The precipitation and rapid growth of grains of TiC in the Tyranno fibres was seen from 1473K [7].

After creep the fibres were seen to possess the same microstructures as after heat treatment at the same temperature with no indications of stress enhanced grain growth or anisotropy [7].

Fig. 11: Fracture Morphology of the LoxM Fibre at 1300°C.

DISCUSSION

A comparison between the microstructures and the thermo-mechanical properties of fibres with high and low oxygen contents confirms the link between oxygen content, the presence of an intergranular phase, grain size, rigidity, chemical stability and creep resistance.

The Hi-Nicalon fibre can be seen to differ markedly from the other fibres in its tensile and creep behaviour. The much lower oxygen content results in a drastic decrease of the

proportion of the low modulus intergranular phase. As a consequence, at room temperature, the Hi-Nicalon fibres show a higher Young's modulus than the other fibres. The grain sizes in the as received fibres and their growth related to their original dimensions, up to 1673K, are higher compared to those of the NLM202 fibres. The very low oxygen content in the grain boundary regions in the Hi-Nicalon does not limit the grain growth as it does in the oxygen rich fibres, but gives to the fibre better creep resistance.

The grain growth at 1673K is also more marked in the Lox-E than in the Lox-M fibre due to the reduction in oxygen content. However the presence of alkoxide groups in the PTC precursor imposes a minimum oxygen concentration at the grain boundary region in the Lox-E fibre so that this fibre behaves in creep in a similar fashion to the fibres cured by oxidation. Moreover the Tyranno fibres appear to be less stabilised as grain growth and shrinkage are seen to begin at lower temperatures than with the Nicalon fibres. The positive contribution of the titanium which was expected in the Tyranno fibres is therefore masked by the excess of oxygen and the lack of stability of the structure.

The duration of pyrolysis or the maximum temperature the fibres experience during manufacture appears to be insufficient for optimum properties to be obtained. The shrinkage seen under low loads at high temperatures is due to an increase in fibre density due to the reduction of porosity, with little contribution coming from grain growth. During the first five hours under steady loading, the deformation behaviour of the fibres is due to two mechanisms which are in competition. This effect, which is more important in the Tyranno fibres, can be reduced by a heat treatment which stabilises the fibre structure. In comparison with these fibres, the NLM202 fibre seems to be more stabilised, as shown by less grain growth and only slight shrinkage.

In passing from 1373K to 1573K, before total degradation, the microstructural changes due to the modification and reduction of the amorphous phases mean that the differences in behaviour of all the fibres become less important. As a consequence, their creep characteristics tend to converge.

CONCLUSIONS

In comparison with the earlier generation of fibres only the Hi-Nicalon fibre represents a real improvement of thermo-mechanical properties, however it still contains excess carbon which, it is reported, leads to a lower creep resistance compared to an experimental stoichiometric fibre [5]. Such modifications will not however suppress external oxidation which becomes significant above 1473K and could have a major effect at high temperatures on the fibre/matrix interface in any composites based on these fibres.

Thanks are due to Dr. A. Thorel for the realisation of the TEM pictures

REFERENCES

- [1] LE COUSTOMER P., MONTHIOUX M., and OBERLIN A. (1993) : "Understanding Nicalon Fibre", *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 11, 95-103.
- [2] SIMON G., BUNSELL A.R. (1984) "Creep behaviour and structural characterisation at high temperatures of Nicalon SiC fibres". *J. Mater. Sci.* 19, 3658-3670.
- [3] OKAMURA K. (1987) "Ceramic fibres from polymer precursors". *Composites* 18 [2] 107-120
- [4] YAMAMURA T., HURUSHIMA T., HURUSHIMA T., KIMOTO M., ISHIKAWA T., SHIBUYA M., IWAI T. (1987) Development of new continuous Si-Ti-C-O fiber with high mechanical strength and heat-resistance, *High Tech Ceramics* (ed. by P. Vincenzini), pp. 737-746. Elsevier Science Publishers.
- [5] ICHIKAWA H., OKAMURA K., SEGUCHI T. (1995) "Oxygen-free ceramic fibers from organosilicon precursors and e-beam curing". *Ceramic Transactions, proceeding of High Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites II* (edited by A.G. Evans), Vol.58, pp. 65-76.
- [6] UBE (1993) "Properties of Tyranno fiber" Technical data report n°2-001001
- [7] HOCHET N., BERGER M.H., BUNSELL A.R. (1997) "Microstructure and thermo-mechanical stability of a low-oxygen Nicalon fibre"q. Under press in *J. Microsc.* 185 [2]